

Application of the Maximal Covering Location Problem to Study the Optimal Distribution of Intervention Units for Offshore Infrastructure Protection

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Abstract—Offshore security faces the challenge of extensive distances between the shore and maritime infrastructures such as offshore wind farms and subsea data cables. At the same time, security forces such as coast guards and navies have limited capabilities to intervene and protect these infrastructures far off the coast, leading to long intervention times and delayed responses. This work investigates whether a strategic distribution of intervention units to offshore infrastructures in German waters can guarantee that every offshore facility is reachable within a certain time frame. We address this problem by formulating and applying the maximal covering location problem (MCLP) to optimize the placement of intervention resources. Our approach aims to maximize the number of offshore wind parks that can be covered within a predefined service distance, thereby ensuring timely responses across all offshore infrastructures.

Index Terms—Offshore infrastructures, protection, optimized coverage, maximal covering location problem.

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of wars and hybrid threats increases the importance of offshore infrastructure protection. Moreover, the green energy transition requires the construction of more offshore wind farms farther away from the shore and from coastal ports, naval bases, and airfields. Additionally, the availability of intervention capabilities to protect offshore infrastructures far off the coast is often limited, leading to prolonged intervention times and delayed incident responses [1].

Calculations and simulations in [2] show that the probability that an intervention unit stationed in a shore-side port reaches an offshore wind farm before a potential threat is very low when the threat is detected close to the attack target. Helicopters are very fast, and the probability that they reach an offshore infrastructure in time to disrupt an attack is therefore higher than that of a vessel. However, depending on how far the helicopter has to travel, the probability of a successful intervention can still be very low, especially if the deployment area is located far from the coast. Even fast intervention assets such as helicopters can thus provide only limited protection for offshore infrastructures.

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Hence, the question arises whether it is possible to place and allocate intervention units to specific offshore infrastructures in such a way that as many infrastructures as possible are covered. This paper considers the following research question:

Is there a nearly optimal solution of the allocation of intervention units to ensure that they can reach all wind farms in the German North Sea within a reasonable time?

We use the maximal covering location problem (MCLP) to study this question and ask how suitable this approach is for the answering of this research question.

Structure of the paper: We start by introducing the MCLP. Then we specify our research question, apply the MCLP to the research question and present the results. To conclude, we summarize our findings and provide an outlook including further research questions and issues.

II. THE MAXIMAL COVERING LOCATION PROBLEM

The MCLP has been introduced by Church and ReVelle in [3]. It was originally used as an optimization problem from combinatorics and location planning. The basic idea and goal is to choose a limited number of locations so that the largest possible number of demand points lies within a given distance or capture radius from at least one chosen location. There are many applications of this problem [4] in areas such as healthcare facility location and coverage (hospitals, clinics, vaccination centers), utilities and critical infrastructure (water, power, gas, telecommunications), transportation and logistics (distribution centers, courier networks, fueling stations) and environmental monitoring and maintenance (air quality stations, weather/hazard monitoring) [5]. The MCLP has also been used for emergency services and response planning (fire, police, EMS) [6] as well as for public safety and disaster management applications (shelters, evacuation planning). For an application of the MCLP to the location of ambulance helicopters see [7]. Moreover, see [8] for the usage of the MCLP in disaster planning, where it is applied for the location-allocation of shelters.

In the following we describe the mathematical formulation of this problem as it is formulated in [3]. We start by introducing the variables that are needed to state the mathematical formulation.

- Let I be the set of demand nodes, that means that it contains all points that should be covered.
- Let J be the set of facility sites, that is the possible nodes where the facilities could be placed.
- Let S be the distance, such that every demand node beyond that distance from a facility is uncovered.
- Let d_{ij} be the distance between the nodes $i \in I$ and $j \in J$.
- For $j \in J$ let

$$x_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if a facility is allocated to node } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

- For each $i \in I$ let $N_i = \{j \in J \mid d_{ij} \leq S\}$ denote the set of possible facility sites that would cover the demand node i .
- For every $i \in I$ let w_i be the weight that is attributed to demand node i .
- Let p be the number of facilities to be located.

Then, using these variables the MCLP can be formulated and is given by:

Maximize

$$z = \sum_{i \in I} w_i y_i \quad (1)$$

such that following conditions hold:

$$\sum_{j \in N_i} x_j \geq y_i \text{ for all } i \in I \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} x_j = p \quad (3)$$

$$x_j \in \{0, 1\} \text{ for all } j \in J \quad (4)$$

$$y_i \in \{0, 1\} \text{ for all } i \in I \quad (5)$$

The main goal that is ensured by (1) is that as many demand nodes as possible are covered, but with a priority for those with higher weights. Additionally, (2) ensures that a demand node is covered if at least one of the facility sites that could cover the demand point has a facility allocated to it and (3) ensures that p facilities are located. Moreover, (4) counts how many facilities are located at point j , in particular this means that there is at most one facility at each facility site. Lastly, (5) indicates whether demand point i is covered or not. More precisely, if $y_i = 1$ then demand node i is covered, else it is not covered.

III. APPLICATION OF THE MCLP

We apply now the MCLP as it was introduced in the previous section. The question that we want to answer with the MCLP is the following:

Regarding the wind farms in the German North Sea and a collection of airports at the shore, is there an

TABLE I
THE WIND FARMS IN THE GERMAN NORTH SEA WITH THEIR CAPACITIES.

i	Wind park	w_i
1	Deutsche Bucht	252 MW
2	Veja Mate	402 MW
3	BARD Offshore 1	400 MW
4	OWP Albatros	112 MW
5	Global Tech 1	400 MW
6	EnBW Hohe See	497 MW
7	Amrumpark West	288 MW
8	Kaskasi	342 MW
9	Nordsee Ost	295 MW
10	Meerwind Süd/Ost	288 MW
11	Gemini 1	300 MW
12	Gemini 2	300 MW
13	Trianel Windpark Borkum	200 MW
14	Trianel Windpark Borkum Phase 2	203 MW
15	Merkur Offshore	396 MW
16	Borkum Riffgrund 1	312 MW
17	Borkum Riffgrund 2	448 MW
18	alpha ventus	60 MW
19	Nordsee One	332 MW
20	Gode Wind 1	330 MW
21	Gode Wind 2	252 MW
22	Gode Wind 3	253 MW
23	Riffgart	108 MW
24	Nordergründe	110 MW
25	Windpark Butendiek	288 MW
26	DanTysk	288 MW
27	Sandbank	288 MW

optimal location of two helicopters such that they can reach as many wind farms as possible in a reasonable amount of time?

We start with our assumptions and formulate them in the words of the MCLP as stated in Section II. After computing the necessary distances, we present the solution of the MCLP.

A. Assumptions

Our demand points are the wind farms in the German North Sea which are listed and numbered in Table I. We consider 27 wind farms, thus let $I = \{1, 2, \dots, 27\}$. We want to prioritize the coverage of wind farms with higher capacity, hence we assume the capacity as the weight that is attributed to the demand node. The capacity data are from openinframap.org and are included in Table I.

Moreover, for the set of facility sites we use the potential bases of the interventions units. Since simulations in [2] show that vessels have no reasonable chance to be in time, here we consider helicopters as intervention capabilities. Therefore, the set J contains the operational airfields and airports where a helicopter could be stationed. They are listed in Table II. Although there are airfields on the islands in the German North Sea that are closer to the wind parks, we consider only airports at the shore because of the easier logistics compared to airports on the islands. Thus we regard in total nine airports, hence let $J = \{1, 2, \dots, 9\}$.

The service distance S of the helicopters is given by the average velocity and the desired intervention time within which the locations should be reached. We assume an average velocity of 240 km/h, since this corresponds roughly to the

TABLE II
THE AIRPORTS AT THE GERMAN NORTH SEA.

j	Airport
1	Husum - Schwesing
2	St. Peter Ording
3	Heide - Büsum
4	Nordholz - Spieka
5	Blexen
6	Jade - Weser
7	Harlesiel
8	Norden - Norddeich
9	Emden

average travel speed of the emergency helicopters used for missions in the German North Sea. Moreover, for the intervention time we assume 20 minutes, a reasonable amount of time considering that intervention times for emergency services in Germany are usually within 15 minutes. [9] Hence it follows that

$$S = 80 \text{ km.}$$

Thus a helicopter covers all wind farms that it can reach within 20 minutes or less after departing from a base and flying with a speed of 240 km/h. Additionally, if limitations like fuel should be considered, this could be done by choosing the service distance with respect to these restrictions.

For the number of facilities where the intervention units are based we assume $p = 2$, meaning that two helicopters can be located at any of the considered airfields, to cover as many wind farms as possible. More precisely, due to the formulation of the MCLP the two helicopters cannot be located at the same airfield.

B. Computations

Now we can determine the distance d_{ij} for all $i \in I$ and $j \in J$. We measured the distances using openseamap.org and collected them in Table III. Further, we marked the distances that are below the service distance of 80 km.

With the distances and the service distance S we determined the set N_i for all $i \in I$. The results are presented in Table IV.

Now the MCLP can be formulated as: Maximize

$$z = w_1 y_1 + w_2 y_2 + \dots + w_{27} y_{27} \quad (6)$$

such that the equations (2), (3), (4) and (5) are fulfilled.

Since for every $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12, 25, 26, 27\}$ the set N_i is empty, the demand nodes 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12, 25, 26, 27 cannot be covered at all and thus it follows that

$$y_i = 0 \text{ for every } i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 11, 12, 25, 26, 27\}.$$

Hence, (6) becomes maximal if $y_i = 1$ for as many $i \in \{7, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24\}$ as possible.

Since facility site 8 covers the most weight and the most wind parks, we locate the first facility there. Regarding the

TABLE III
THE DISTANCES d_{ij} IN KM WITH MARKINGS FOR $\leq 80 \text{ km}$.

$i \backslash j$	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	218	188	203	195	199	173	148	118	139
2	212	182	197	190	195	169	144	115	136
3	205	176	191	186	191	166	140	113	135
4	187	159	176	175	183	161	134	113	138
5	179	152	169	170	179	157	130	111	137
6	182	153	170	168	176	154	127	106	131
7	92	68	88	104	122	116	91	104	130
8	93	67	87	101	119	112	87	100	126
9	94	67	86	98	115	108	83	95	121
10	94	65	82	92	110	102	76	90	116
11	208	175	187	173	173	145	122	88	106
12	218	185	197	183	183	155	132	97	114
13	182	148	160	146	148	121	97	66	89
14	178	145	157	144	147	120	96	67	90
15	176	142	153	140	142	115	91	62	85
16	179	144	155	139	139	111	88	56	78
17	182	148	158	141	141	113	90	57	78
18	174	139	150	136	138	111	86	57	80
19	162	127	137	122	123	97	72	46	71
20	150	115	126	112	115	90	64	45	72
21	146	112	124	112	117	94	67	51	78
22	142	107	118	105	110	87	60	46	73
23	196	160	167	143	137	106	88	48	60
24	98	63	60	32	41	38	27	68	80
25	104	98	120	150	172	170	146	159	184
26	143	133	155	179	199	191	165	168	195
27	165	154	176	197	215	205	178	176	203

TABLE IV
THE SETS N_i .

i	N_i
1	\emptyset
2	\emptyset
3	\emptyset
4	\emptyset
5	\emptyset
6	\emptyset
7	$\{2\}$
8	$\{2\}$
9	$\{2\}$
10	$\{2, 7\}$
11	\emptyset
12	\emptyset
13	$\{8\}$
14	$\{8\}$
15	$\{8\}$
16	$\{8, 9\}$
17	$\{8, 9\}$
18	$\{8, 9\}$
19	$\{7, 8, 9\}$
20	$\{7, 8, 9\}$
21	$\{7, 8, 9\}$
22	$\{7, 8, 9\}$
23	$\{8, 9\}$
24	$\{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$
25	\emptyset
26	\emptyset
27	\emptyset

remaining wind parks, that facility site 8 cannot cover, it follows that facility site 2 covers the most, hence we choose to locate the second facility there. Adding the second helicopter increases the coverage from 12 to 16 wind parks and the covered weight is increased by 1213 MW. In particular, it follows that this choice of facility sites 2 and 8 covers every wind park, that can be covered depending on our assumptions. Hence, with

$$x_2 = x_8 = 1 \text{ and } x_j = 0 \text{ for every } j \in J - \{2, 8\}$$

and

$$y_i = 1 \text{ for every}$$

$$i \in \{7, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24\}$$

all conditions are fulfilled and equation (6) is maximized.

Since all wind parks, that could be covered with this service distance, are covered by the choice of facility sites, the actual weight of the wind parks is not relevant for the solution. This would have come into account, if the choice had to be made which wind farms the intervention helicopter should cover.

C. Result

To conclude, we summarize our assumptions:

- We want to cover as many wind farms in the German North Sea as possible.
- We regard helicopters with an average speed of 240 km/h.
- We want to locate two helicopters at different airports on the shore.
- The service distance of the helicopters is 20 minutes.

It follows that the two best airports are St. Peter Ording and Norden - Norddeich. If the helicopters are stationed at those airports, every wind farm, that can be reached from any of the considered airports in 20 minutes, is covered. In particular, we obtain a coverage of 59,26% of the wind parks in the German North Sea with the allocation of two helicopters to these airports. On the other hand, 40,74% of the wind parks are too far off the shore to be reached in 20 minutes. Thus either the service distance has to be increased, the helicopters have to be faster, or the helicopters have to be located offshore to obtain a higher coverage.

Furthermore, when studying Table III it is striking that if the service distance of the helicopters would be 40 minutes, then every considered wind farm in the German North Sea could be reached by a helicopter with an average speed of 240 km/h from the airports in Norden - Norddeich and St. Peter Ording. Moreover, most wind parks could be reached from the airport in Norden - Norddeich within 30 minutes with a helicopter with an average speed of 240 km/h.

IV. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The MCLP can be used to support decision-making. The analysis enables operators to optimize the distribution of intervention assets based on specific scenario parameters and assumptions. In particular, the two airports that our analysis identified are in fact the same airports where rescue helicopters

for offshore wind farms are currently stationed, thus verifying - at least in part - the MCLP model and results presented in this paper. It is possible, then to ensure efficient intervention coverage of many wind parks in the German North Sea.

However, the sets of the demand nodes and facility sites are so small that it seems that the full capabilities of the MCLP do not come into effect in our application. In particular, the best solution is immediately apparent from the data and hence in this case the analysis does not improve the result significantly. Nevertheless, for larger and more complex problems the analysis with MCLP would be beneficial.

Hence, the MCLP is suitable for the location of facilities in the maritime domain. Depending on the concrete research question it might also be reasonable to regard further developments of the MCLP. An introduction to other covering models and their extensions can be found in [10].

In most cases, the MCLP is viewed as a binary question and a point is either covered or not, but there are approaches where a gradual coverage is considered. For example in [11] the location of the infrastructure for urban air mobility, which are called vertiports, is studied. Their aim is the identification of optimal locations for the vertiports, such that as many people as possible live within a short distance to the next vertiport. In the location problem of intervention units in maritime security, it might be reasonable to consider gradual coverage, since not only the coverage but also the time that is needed to reach specific offshore locations is crucial.

In [12] gradual coverage is interpreted as two radii, the lower radius indicating full coverage and between the two radii the coverage decreases gradually until there is no coverage outside the greater radius. Moreover, the radii do not need to be fixed but can vary according to distributions of assets and locations that are independent of each other. In the uniform case, assuming a range around a traditional cover radius, they provide an explicit formula for the calculation of the expected cover. Additionally, in their approach they allow different radii for each point. This might be an effective approach when considering different intervention units.

To conclude, the MCLP is a powerful tool not only for logistics but also in the maritime security settings. And if new wind farms are constructed in the German North Sea, then such an analysis could support the decisions where to allocate intervention units. Moreover, a regular analysis could include changes and perhaps improve current situations.

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